

EBFMC25-OP-06 · Evaluation of the Relationship Between Anemia and Polypharmacy in Individuals Aged 80 Years and Older

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anemia and polypharmacy are common conditions in the geriatric population and are associated with decreased functional capacity and increased demand for healthcare services (Guralnik et al., 2004; Maher et al., 2014). The coexistence of these conditions may further complicate the health status of elderly individuals. This study aimed to evaluate the relationship between anemia and polypharmacy in individuals aged 80 years and older.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted between March and April 2025 at the Healthy Aging Center of a tertiary care hospital. Data from 106 patients were retrospectively reviewed, including age, sex, comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, chronic kidney disease, malignancy, Alzheimer's disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease), number of medications used, Katz Index of Independence in Activities of Daily Living, Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living Scale, and Clinical Frailty Scale scores. Hemoglobin levels at the time of admission were obtained from laboratory records. Polypharmacy was defined as the use of five or more medications per day (Masnoon et al., 2017). Anemia was defined based on World Health Organization criteria: Hb <12 g/dL in women and <13 g/dL in men (World Health Organization [WHO], 2011).

Results: Anemia was present in 42.6% (n=45) and polypharmacy in 55.7% (n=59) of the participants. The prevalence of polypharmacy was significantly higher among anemic individuals (67.3%) compared to non-anemic ones (42.1%) (p=0.009). Anemic individuals were older and more likely to be male (87.5±3.9 vs. 85.8±3.4 years, p=0.016; 51.0% vs. 24.6%, p=0.005). There were no statistically significant differences in comorbidities, Katz, Lawton, and frailty scores between the two groups (p≥0.05). Logistic regression analysis identified polypharmacy (OR: 2.9 [1.2–6.9], p=0.017), older age (OR: 1.2 [1.1–1.4], p=0.005), and male sex (OR: 3.7 [1.5–9.2], p=0.005) as independent predictors of anemia.

Conclusion: Polypharmacy is an independent risk factor for anemia among individuals aged 80 years and older, regardless of age and sex. Medication management in older adults should be approached holistically, including an assessment of anemia risk (Onder et al., 2007).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Polypharmacy, anemia, geriatrics

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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